

THE PRINCIPLE OF SEPARATION OF LOCAL POWERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Yakubjonov Nuriddin Ravshan o'g'li

Tashkent State University of Law

“Public Administration Law”

Master's student

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Improving public administration, ensuring citizens' rights and freedoms, and creating an effective and transparent governance system at the local level are among the priority directions of modern reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan. From this perspective, an in-depth study of the content and significance of the principle of separation of powers at the local level is becoming a crucial scientific and practical issue today. Moreover, in recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing extensive reforms to put the principle of separation of powers into practice at the local level. However, there are still legal gaps and institutional challenges in this area, which require scientifically and theoretically grounded approaches for their effective resolution.

The traditional founders of the “classical” form of the theory of separation of powers are John Locke and Charles Louis Montesquieu. The English philosopher John Locke (1632-1704) advanced the idea of separation of powers in his work “Two Treatises of Government.” The division of powers into legislative, executive, and federal types, according to Locke, is one of the most important means of ensuring human rights. In this case, “all are subject to the legislative power, as it is the supreme body capable of establishing laws”[1].

The French philosopher Montesquieu (1689-1755), in his work “The Spirit of the Laws,” put forward the doctrine of the “Separation of Powers.” The fundamental principle of the concept of separation of powers is that state power should not be concentrated in one body, and the principle of limiting power with power is considered the foundation of a democratic state. In his view, when all power is concentrated in one hand, despotism emerges[2].

In the modern interpretation of the principle of separation of powers, this principle encompasses not only the division of national state power into various branches but also mutual balance and oversight. As the American political scientist Robert Dahl noted, “The separation of powers is not just the distribution of power, but the establishment of institutional safeguards against the abuse of power.”[3]

According to the Russian legal scholar S.A. Avakyan, from a historical perspective, the need to divide the branches of government and define the

directions and powers for each of them enables the practical implementation of the government's tasks and functions. At the same time, the separation of powers increases the demand for governmental accountability, the effectiveness of its operations, and the resolution of existing problems. Such a separation entails a clear and distinct definition of each authority's responsibilities without affecting the unity of powers. Instead, it grants each branch the right to monitor and complement the activities of others, and, when necessary, to exercise control. This arrangement of interactions between the authorities has historically evolved and is known as the system of "checks and balances"[4]. Here, we can see that the ability of power branches to control each other while maintaining their independence is considered a fundamental condition and principle of democracy. In other words, if one party acts in pursuit of its own interests, the other party independently monitors and ensures democracy.

As the legal scholar Ya.Y. Ollamov emphasized, the distinctive features of the concept of the local government system are such that it requires comprehensive, in-depth scientific study and interpretation from its researchers. This is because this process develops and improves dialectically in accordance with the main goal of society and the requirements of a specific period. Therefore, scientific and practical conclusions about the role and essence of the local government system can only be determined on the basis of thorough and comprehensive scientific research[5].

After Uzbekistan gained independence, significant steps were taken towards democratizing the public administration system. The principle of separation of powers was enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 8, 1992 (Constitution, Article 11). According to this principle, power is exercised through legislative, executive, and judicial branches.

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, emphasized the following: "The main objectives of establishing representative and executive bodies of local state authority are, firstly: to ensure public participation in forming state bodies in these areas; secondly, to discuss issues of local importance collectively and make appropriate decisions; thirdly, to establish oversight over the activities of executive bodies at the local level"[6].

Although Uzbekistan has implemented significant reforms during its years of independence to democratize the public administration system and increase the autonomy of local government bodies, in the initial years of the local governance system, khokims (governors) chaired the councils of people's

deputies, meaning that both representative and executive powers were concentrated in one hand. This led to the incomplete implementation of the principle of separation of powers, resulting in insufficient balance and independence in local governance.

Amendments and additions were introduced to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in a new edition by national referendum on April 30, 2023, aimed at separating the powers of executive and representative bodies of local state authority. As a result of these changes, the authority of the khokim (governor) to chair the councils in regions, districts, and cities was abolished. We can see that this was intended to ensure a government based on people-oriented governance.

To conduct a deep analysis of the content and essence of the principle of separation of powers at the local level, it is important, first and foremost, to identify its main elements. This principle envisions the functioning of the following main bodies in local governance, namely according to Articles 120-121 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state power at the local level is exercised through the following main bodies:

Article 120: The representative bodies of state power are the Councils of People's Deputies in regions, districts, and cities (except for cities subordinate to districts);

Article 121: The local executive authority is represented by khokimiyats, which exercise executive power in the respective territory[7].

According to Professor O.T. Khusanov, "The principle of separation of powers plays a decisive role in the formation of the local government system. This results in the establishment of two independent bodies at the local level: representative bodies and executive authorities"[8]. In agreement with this view, local representative bodies are organs elected by the population on a representative basis, responsible for resolving issues of local significance and overseeing the activities of executive bodies. Local executive bodies, in turn, are accountable for territorial development, implementation of economic and social programs, and execution of state policy at the local level.

The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, stated: "Without a strong executive power, even the most democratically adopted decisions may not be implemented" [9].

According to Z.Vakhidov, the main aspect of the principle of separation of local government is that each government should have the opportunity and the right to control other government entities. Researcher Sh.Khamdamova

disagrees with this opinion, not mutual control, but the system of mutual restraint of powers and maintaining a balance of interests, ensuring the independence and freedom of the branches of government, the interaction and balance of power branches, is an important component of this principle. In this case, the researcher should assign a wide range of supervisory functions to representative bodies of local authorities[10]. Agreeing with the opinion of the researcher Sh.Khamdamova, the principle of separation of powers ensures the independence of government bodies, but also maintains balance and justice in public administration through their mutual coordination and control. The expanded oversight function of representative bodies serves to ensure legality and transparency.

The principle of “Strong Council, accountable and proactive khokim,” introduced by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-28 dated February 2, 2024 “On Measures to Increase the Effectiveness of Local Government Bodies,” represents the modern implementation of the classical concept of separation of powers in Uzbekistan’s local governance system[11].

The principle of “Strong Council, accountable and proactive khokim” encompasses the following main directions:

Firstly, the concept of a “Strong Council” envisions the Council of People’s Deputies functioning as a fully independent body. The Council organizes its activities without interference from the executive branch and makes decisions autonomously. The Council’s oversight powers have been significantly expanded, granting it the authority to approve the appointment of the governor and hear reports on their activities. The Council exercises complete control over the local budget, performing the functions of approving, amending, and monitoring its implementation. The Council establishes a separate apparatus to support its operations and possesses independent financial resources.

Secondly, the principle of an “Accountable Governor” establishes the obligation for the head of the executive branch to report regularly to the Council. The governor is required to ensure full transparency in their activities and openly disclose all important information to the public.

Thirdly, the concept of “Proactive Governor” requires the head of the executive branch to propose innovative approaches and new ideas for regional development. The governor is responsible for actively attracting investments, conducting negotiations with potential investors, and developing investment projects. The governor must take initiative in solving problems of local importance.

Within the framework of the new system, the structure of local government has been fundamentally restructured. The Council of People's Deputies elects a chairman and deputy chairmen from among its members. The governor's function of chairing the Council has been abolished. The Council establishes permanent commissions in various areas - including budget, social issues, legal matters, and others. Each commission is tasked with overseeing the activities of the governor's office in its respective area. The Council will form its own apparatus, including a secretariat, legal department, and analytical group, and will have an independent budget.

The structure of the hokimiyat has also been reorganized. The Hokim is appointed by the President but is fully accountable to the Council for their activities. The Hokim manages the executive apparatus, all departments and administrations, and sector hokims. The main function of the Hokim is to implement state policy at the local level, which is carried out under the supervision of the Council and in cooperation with it. This system ensures the real implementation of the principle of separation of powers at the local level. The Council performs the oversight function, while the Hokim performs the executive function. Both bodies operate independently within their competencies, while ensuring effective governance through mechanisms of cooperation. This approach serves to strengthen the democratic foundations of local governance and increase its effectiveness.

The powers, interactions, and control mechanisms of these bodies are regulated by specific legislative acts. For the effective implementation of the principle of separation of powers, balance, independence, and cooperation between representative and executive bodies are of crucial importance. This allows, on the one hand, to protect the interests of citizens in local governance, and on the other hand, to effectively implement state policies at the local level.

The practical significance of the principle of separation of powers at the local level is that it serves to increase the effectiveness of public administration, guarantee the rights and freedoms of citizens, strengthen transparency and accountability in governance, and prevent corruption and abuse. Through local councils, citizens' participation in governance is expanded, their interests are protected, and executive bodies are held accountable to the councils for their activities. This will prevent the concentration of state power in one hand and enable the provision of balance and effective cooperation in local governance.

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